

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc
hash://md5/b35f426dc3f179e1168f61989945bd67

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
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<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/contribute>
<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc, has fingerprint hash://md5/b35f426dc3f179e1168f61989945bd67, is 11.8MiB in size and contains 8,688 interactions with 4 unique types of associations (e.g., interactsWith) between 746 primary taxa (e.g., Gelechiidae) and 380 associated taxa (e.g., Oak). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

San Diego Natural History Museum <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc/archive/7238d8b804f543250eb487b43144e1125fb3688a.zip>
 2026-01-24T06:05:59.798Z hash://md5/b35f426dc3f179e1168f61989945bd67

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.4
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 11.8MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc`)

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
<code>biblio.bib</code>	list of bibliographic reference of this review
<code>check-dataset.sh</code>	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
<code>data.zip</code>	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
<code>index.docx</code>	review in MS Word format
<code>index.html</code>	review in HTML format
<code>index.md</code>	review in Pandoc markdown format
<code>index.pdf</code>	review in PDF format
<code>indexed-citations.csv.gz</code>	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
<code>indexed-citations.html.gz</code>	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
<code>indexed-citations.tsv.gz</code>	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
<code>indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg</code>	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/sdnhm-sdmc`, has fingerprint hash: `://md5/b35f426dc3f179e1168f61989945bd67`, is 11.8MiB in size and contains 8,688 interactions with 4 unique types of associations (e.g., `interactsWith`) between 746 primary taxa (e.g., `Gelechiidae`) and 380 associated taxa (e.g., `Oak`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in `gzipped csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the `gzipped html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Poanes melane	interactsWith	Aira caespitosa	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index
Tortricidae	interactsWith	Pine	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index
Tortricidae	hasHost	diseased pine tree	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index
Argyrotaenia citrana	interactsWith	Christmas cactus	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
interactsWith	8159
adjacentTo	440
hasHost	88
eats	1

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Gelechiidae	292
Orthosia erythrolita	192
Glaucina epiphysaria	169
Malacosoma californicum andreasum	162
Plataea personaria	145
Gnorimoschema	136
Apodemia mormo	132
Hymenoptera	122
Stannodes annellata	118
Zenophleps lignicolorata	109
Ethmia discostrigella	104
Miodera stigmata	102
Amydria	96
Eucosma pulveratana	92
Notarctia proxima	80
Stannodes coenonymphata	79
Grammia ornata	78
Speranza marcescaria	77
Pherne subpunctata	67

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Oak	2100
Sycamore	1885
Sage	1327
Willow	853

targetTaxonName	count
Manzanita	516
Coleogyne ramosissima	153
Hemizonia conjugens	103
Bebbia	86
Eriogonum fasciculatum	69
Bebbia flowers	63
Pogogyne nudiuscula	45
Pine	44
Penstemon	42
Yucca	40
Baccharis sarothroides	36
Alfalfa	33
Foeniculum vulgare	26
Lasthenia californica	24
Eriogonum	21

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Gelechiidae	interactsWith	Sycamore	95
Gelechiidae	interactsWith	Sage	83
Gelechiidae	interactsWith	Oak	75
Malacosoma californicum andreasum	interactsWith	Coleogyne ramosissima	75
Malacosoma californicum andreasum	hasHost	Coleogyne ramosissima	75
Apodemia mormo	interactsWith	Bebbia	66
Orthosia erythrolita	interactsWith	Sycamore	58
Stannodes annellata	interactsWith	Oak	57
Stannodes annellata	interactsWith	Sycamore	56
Apodemia mormo	adjacentTo	Bebbia flowers	55
Glaucina epiphysaria	interactsWith	Sage	51

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Ethmia discostrigella	interactsWith	Sycamore	50
Ethmia discostrigella	interactsWith	Oak	50
Glaucina epiphysaria	interactsWith	Sycamore	49
Plataea personaria	interactsWith	Sage	49
Gnorimoschema	interactsWith	Willow	46
Orthosia erythrolita	interactsWith	Oak	44
Gnorimoschema	interactsWith	Sage	43
Miodera stigmata	interactsWith	Sage	43

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download [svg](#)

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at [indexed-interactions.gpkg](#) for point data and [indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg](#) for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Anobiidae	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Anobiidae
Anticarsia gemmatalis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Anticarsia gemmatalis
Anticarsia gemmatalis	SYNONYM_OF	col	Anticarsia acutilinea
Anticarsia gemmatalis	SYNONYM_OF	col	Anticarsia anisospila

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	325
col	family	44
col	genus	107
col	infraspecific name	1
col	kingdom	1
col	order	4
col	species	557
col	subfamily	8
col	subgenus	1
col	subspecies	19
col	subtribe	1
col	superfamily	1
col	tribe	2
col	variety	3

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
discoverlife	NA	1055
discoverlife	species	12
gbif	NA	232
gbif	family	46
gbif	genus	118
gbif	kingdom	1
gbif	order	4
gbif	species	625
gbif	subspecies	49
gbif	variety	7
itis	NA	375
itis	family	44
itis	genus	87
itis	kingdom	1
itis	order	4
itis	phylum	1
itis	species	485
itis	subfamily	9
itis	suborder	1
itis	subspecies	53
itis	superfamily	1
itis	superorder	1
itis	tribe	1
itis	variety	6
mdd	NA	1067
ncbi	NA	375
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	44
ncbi	genus	102
ncbi	order	4
ncbi	species	501
ncbi	subfamily	9
ncbi	subgenus	4
ncbi	suborder	1
ncbi	subspecies	26
ncbi	superfamily	1
ncbi	tribe	2
pbdb	NA	977
pbdb	family	40
pbdb	genus	30
pbdb	infraclass	1
pbdb	infraorder	1
pbdb	kingdom	1
pbdb	order	4

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	species	3
pbdb	subfamily	9
pbdb	suborder	1
pbdb	superfamily	1
tpt	NA	1067
wfo	NA	899
wfo	genus	66
wfo	species	98
wfo	subspecies	4
wfo	variety	1
worms	NA	914
worms	family	31
worms	genus	45
worms	kingdom	1
worms	order	4
worms	species	71
worms	suborder	1

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	715
col	SYNONYM_OF	100
col	NONE	370
discoverlife	NONE	1114
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	11
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	7
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	804
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	194
gbif	NONE	275
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	673
itis	NONE	420
itis	SYNONYM_OF	35
mdd	NONE	1126
ncbi	SAME_AS	669
ncbi	NONE	420

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	44
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	4
pbdb	NONE	1029
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	96
tpt	NONE	1126
wfo	NONE	944
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	164
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	31
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	3
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	151
worms	NONE	968
worms	SYNONYM_OF	16

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that

document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-29T03:23:14Z	note	found unsupported interaction type with name: [attacked by]
2026-01-29T03:23:15Z	note	source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder
2026-01-29T03:23:15Z	note	source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder
2026-01-29T03:23:15Z	note	source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder	46
found unsupported interaction type with name: [attacked by]	1
found unsupported interaction type with name: [15]	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-01-29) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

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Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

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